

Environmental potential of food waste-derived bioplastics

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The rapid growth of plastics manufacturing has intensified climate, ecosystem, and human health pressures, urging for sustainable solutions. Bioplastics have emerged as a prominent mitigation measure, particularly sourced from food waste (FW). Conceptually, FW-derived bioplastics are considered environmentally benign, but their environmental performance is highly context-dependent. This review summarizes recent advances in life cycle assessments (LCA) of relevant bioplastics. While FW as feedstocks is environmentally beneficial, the obtained bioplastics are frequently constrained by energy- and chemical-intensive conversions and by uncertainties during downstream handling. Also, the environmental benefits are non-uniform across impact categories and may involve trade-offs, particularly when background energy systems, purification intensity, and end-of-life assumptions are not aligned with the intended circularity strategy. Future research should prioritize cradle-to-grave, scenario-based LCA. Integrating scale-up, utility recovery, regional waste systems, and harmonized reporting will credibly guide policy and technology toward genuinely circular, low-impact bioplastic systems.

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Introduction

The rapid growth of plastics manufacturing (Fig. 1a) has intensified climate, ecosystem, and human health pressures through the use of fossil resources, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and persistent pollution, including

emerging microplastics and even nanoplastics [1–3]. It is estimated that 52 million metric tonnes of plastic waste are mismanaged globally every year, leaking into soils, rivers, and oceans, primarily via inadequate collection, littering, or uncontrolled disposal [4]. To alleviate the plastic crisis, the world urges sustainable solutions, such as a feedstock shift to renewable biomass and a systematic transformation of end-of-life (EoL) strategies [5].

Bioplastics (bio-based and/or biodegradable polymers) have emerged as a prominent mitigation measure [7]. In particular, bioplastics derived from food waste (FW) offer a distinct rationale for a circular economy. Given the massive generation (Fig. 1b), food loss and waste account for 8–10 % of annual GHG emissions, nearly five times the total emissions from the aviation sector, and contribute to substantial biodiversity loss, using up almost a third of the world's agricultural land [6,8]. Thus, FW-derived bioplastics valorise these unavoidable organic residues, potentially reduce landfill burdens, and avoid (or reduce) the land- and fertilizer-intensive cultivation associated with first-generation feedstocks [9,10].

Conceptually, FW-derived bioplastics are considered environmentally benign, but in reality, their environmental performance is highly context-dependent, proven by relevant life cycle assessments (LCA) [11], [12**]. In current scenarios, the environmental potential of FW-derived bioplastics is largely associated with the minimal impact achievable with optimized processes, sequestration benefits in intended EoL route against existing practices, and the robustness of supporting LCA evidence. Thus, this review summarises recent advances in relevant environmental studies, critically analysing the potential of FW toward a circular and low-impact plastic economy.

Bioplastics from FW

FW and agri-food residues (e.g., bread waste, dairy side streams, orchard residues, vegetable trimmings) contain lignocellulosics, sugars, lipids, and proteins that can be converted into polymer building blocks or used directly as film-forming matrices for plastics. The general framework for deriving bioplastics from FW involves collection and pretreatment to remove contaminants, extraction and conversion of valuable components such as starch, sugars, and lipids into monomers or precursors,

Figure 1

a) Worldwide plastic production, including recycled, from 2018 to 2024. b) Global food waste generation in 2022 [6].

polymerization of the precursors, and compounding and processing into various bioplastics. Fig. 2 summarizes key examples of bioplastics derived from FW.

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are one of the most mature bioplastics, as various FW can be acidogenically fermented to volatile fatty acids (VFAs) or hydrolysed into fermentable sugars and then upgraded by microbial cultures to intracellular PHA [14]. Resultant yield of up to 87 % PHA content have been reported with optimized fermentation processes using VFAs from FW [15]. Similarly, polylactic acid (PLA) can be obtained from FW through fermentation to lactic acid, followed by lactide synthesis and ring-opening polymerization [16]. A recent work reported the utilization of FW for lactic acid production, while integrated carbon quantum dot synthesis from the resulting residue, facilitating a zero-waste FW biorefinery strategy [17*]. Given the relatively strong research over the past decade, a notable trend in FW-derived PHA and PLA is shifting from proof-of-concept lab demonstrations toward industrial-scale process modelling coupled with techno-economic analysis (TEA) and LCA, explicitly identifying utility demand, downstream purification, and regional energy mix as dominant hotspots [18,19].

Beyond PHA and PLA, lipid-rich FW streams are positioned as valuable feedstocks for polyurethane (PU). A recent FW biorefinery scheme converted FW lipids into polyols via epoxidation and oxirane ring-opening, enabling the formulation of rigid PU foams with properties suitable for insulation applications [20*,21].

Notably, a follow-up study assessed the environmental benefits and trade-offs of valorising FW into polyols for rigid PU foams, providing a template for how 'drop-in' waste-derived plastics should be treated in LCA, especially with respect to EoL modelling and avoided burden choices [22].

Food waste also supports a broader class of starch- and cellulose-based bioplastics, which can be particularly relevant for packaging films and coatings [23]. For instance, starch extracted from potato peels has been used to form glycerol-plasticized biplastic films, illustrating a straightforward route from post-consumer potato peel waste to thermoplastic starch materials [24]. Cellulosic fractions from FW, when chemically modified, are used to reinforce films or serve as a film matrix in biplastic applications [25]. Protein-rich side streams provide another pathway. Researchers demonstrated the industrial-scale production of self-standing, transparent, and flexible biplastic films based on soy whey and okara, two pivotal protein-rich byproducts from tofu manufacturing [26].

Besides, an emerging opportunity is to utilise FW as a feedstock for production of conventional platform monomers in bio-based plastic synthesis. Recent work demonstrates, for example, that FW can be converted into ethylene glycol, a key monomer for polyethylene terephthalate (PET), suggesting a credible route toward partially or fully bio-based PET analogues when paired with renewable terephthalic acid streams [27,28]. Glucose derived from FW can be catalytically

Figure 2

Examples of bioplastics obtained from food waste [7,13]. Abbreviations: PU, polyurethane; PHA, polyhydroxyalkanoate; PLA, polylactic acid; PET, polyethylene terephthalate; PBS, polybutylene succinate; PEF, polyethylene furanoate.

transformed into hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and subsequently upgraded to 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA), the monomer used for polyethylene furanoate (PEF), as shown for pineapple waste streams [29].

Overall environmental benefits & specific burdens

Conventional fossil-based plastics are intrinsically linked to fossil extraction and refining, and their life-

cycle climate impacts are amplified by high production volumes, energy-intensive polymer manufacturing, and the persistence of plastic waste stocks. Against this baseline, FW-derived bioplastics are frequently framed as environmentally advantageous due to three primary reasons, which will be illustrated below.

First, FW-derived bioplastics offset the use of fossil resources, particularly fossil carbon, in compared with

conventional plastic materials. Since FW is, by definition, residual biomass, diverting it into polymer production effectively alleviates fossil resource scarcity. For example, Kim et al. showed that waste-derived PLA pathways were generally carbon negative when displacing PET or HDPE [30]. Compared with bio-based plastics made from dedicated crops, using FW as feedstock avoided upstream agricultural burdens, reducing impacts associated with land occupation, fertilizer and pesticide inputs, irrigation, and field emissions [31]. Thus, these feedstock substitutions set the foundation for why FW-derived bioplastics are considered environmentally benign.

The second benefit is that the use of FW diverts organic waste from its original fate, which is in general landfill or incineration. By modelling this diversion in relevant LCA studies and counting it into the statistics, FW-derived bioplastics in general could lead to substantially reduced GHG emissions and global warming potential (GWP). A recent LCA work shows that waste-to-PHA biorefineries can achieve markedly improved outcomes under plausible future improvements in yields, recovery efficiencies, and background energy systems, illustrating that the environmental opportunity is strongly coupled to technological learning and decarbonization trajectories [32]. In addition, the environmental benefits can be further enhanced if these FW-derived bioplastics are biodegradable or compostable, potentially reducing impacts in the EoL stage [33].

Despite the above-mentioned benefits, FW as the feedstock for bioplastics may also bring additional burdens. Across LCA and other environmental modelling studies, utilities and chemicals required for pretreatment, conversion, and purification repeatedly dominate the impact profile [34]. A cradle-to-gate LCA of lactic acid from bread waste showed that energy integration and purification strategy materially influence GWP and other categories, and that chemical inputs linked to pH control and downstream operations can become significant contributors, illustrating how strongly environmental performance depends on fermentation configuration and downstream separations [35]. Neutralization agents, nutrient supplements, solvents for extraction, and polymer recovery steps may shift impacts toward toxicity, eutrophication, or resource use categories [36]. This phenomenon is often linked to relevant TEA studies: these major environmental burdens (energy-/chemical-intensive conversions) are also primary cost drivers, reducing the economic viability of FW-derived bioplastics.

A further burden is inherited from FW heterogeneity. FW composition fluctuates seasonally and geographically and may contain contaminants from co-collected

packaging, requiring robust pretreatment (e.g., homogenization, pH control, sterilization, additional wastewater handling) that raises energy demand and emissions. In addition, the baseline waste management counterfactual (landfill, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion) and the accounting for avoided burdens can strongly shape conclusions, meaning that attributional comparisons are sensitive to regional waste policy and infrastructure [22].

In summary, studies have shown FW-derived bioplastics could support a more sustainable polymer industry, but only to some degree [31,37]. LCA evidence increasingly indicates that the magnitude of the benefit depends on how waste credits are handled, how energy- and chemical-intensive conversion steps are designed, and whether EoL pathways and local infrastructure are consistent with the intended degradability or recyclability of the polymer [38,39]. Without careful analysis, one may overstate the environmental potential of FW-derived plastics [40].

Limitations and challenges

Many LCA studies of FW-derived bioplastics converge on a similar qualitative conclusion: upstream feedstock substitution could bring substantial benefits, but additional burdens may exist in the overall system. This ambiguity could even be exaggerated by the recurring flaws and limitations in current LCA studies, particularly in relation to the methodologies.

The first limitation lies in life-cycle boundary choices and the frequent reliance on cradle-to-gate scopes. Although early-stage studies often adopt narrow boundaries to focus on conversion performance, mounting methodological scrutiny indicates that plastic EoL modeling in LCAs is commonly simplified, with deviations in how recycling, transport, composition, and waste-management practices are represented. A systematic assessment of EoL modeling assumptions for plastic packaging LCAs found substantial inconsistencies and simplifications that can significantly affect conclusions [41**].

Second, biogenic carbon accounting must be handled transparently, otherwise diminishing comparability across studies. Some studies assume an offset of environmental impact when FW is diverted from its original fate to the production of bioplastics, but some does not [42,43]. Inconsistent handling of avoided burden credits for diverted FW, allocation among co-products, and functional unit definitions can lead to contradictory conclusions even for similar technologies. Recent methodological recommendations for LCA of recyclable plastics emphasize harmonized functional units, careful treatment of allocation, and explicit reporting of assumptions to avoid arbitrary or incomparable results

[44]. Applying such guidance to FW-derived bioplastics is essential for future development and scaling up.

A significant challenge associated with LCA studies of FW-derived bioplastics is related to the realism of product EoL, environmental fate, and interactions with existing circular systems. First, the biodegradability of FW-derived bioplastics is highly case-dependent, and degradation rates observed in standardized tests may not reflect their fate in the environment. It is reported that degradation performance depends strongly on polymer type and environmental conditions, and that laboratory biodegradation evidence can overstate degradation speed and completeness [45]. Second, even when biodegradation occurs, trade-offs among impact categories may arise. A recent study quantifying the environmental impacts of biodegradable microplastics reported that highly biodegradable microplastics can reshape the microbial community and metabolic pathways, thereby exacerbating the emissions of N₂O and

CH₄ in urban lake sediments more than traditional microplastics [46]. Third, bio-based and biodegradable plastics can complicate mechanical recycling if sorting is insufficient. Even modest PLA contamination in a HDPE recycling system can substantially degrade the properties of recycled HDPE [47*]. Finally, for FW-derived PU, which is not typically biodegradable, environmental performance depends on feasible recycling strategies and the impact profile of waste treatment. Recent work assessing the environmental potential of chemical recycling of PU rigid foam shows that the EoL technology choice can be as consequential as feedstock origin [48]. These issues strongly complicate the handling of EoL fate of FW-derived plastics if a cradle-to-grave LCA is anticipated.

Finally, emerging issues related to standards are becoming increasingly relevant to credibility and transparency, particularly regarding biogenic carbon accounting and climate metrics for bio-based materials. A

Figure 3

Recommendations for future environmental studies of bioplastics derived from food waste. Abbreviations: LCA, life cycle assessment; EoL, end-of-life.

recent review of LCA-related standards highlights that approaches to biogenic carbon and its contribution to GWP differ across frameworks, which can strongly influence reported climate results, including FW-derived bioplastics [49*]. In parallel, practical barriers in waste management, such as limited acceptance of biodegradable plastics in existing systems, inadequate labeling and sorting, and misalignment between material design and local treatment capacity, continue to constrain real-world performance and should be reflected in scenario design rather than treated as externalities [50].

Future LCA of FW-derived bioplastics should move decisively toward harmonized, decision-relevant assessments that reflect both technological maturity and real-world waste management constraints, as shown in Fig. 3. Methodologically, studies should adopt cradle-to-grave boundaries as the default, implement region-specific foreground inventories for sorting, pretreatment, conversion, and especially EoL operations, and transparently justify counterfactual waste management baselines and marginal substitution assumptions. If there are any difficulties, researchers should proceed with scenario studies to compare effects, rather than relying on simple assumptions. Consistent reporting of functional units, clear allocation rules for multi-functional biorefineries, and explicit treatment of biogenic carbon are also necessary to improve comparability and prevent overstated climate benefits. Moreover, EoL modeling should better represent operational realities by incorporating infrastructure availability, sorting losses, and contamination effects on recycling and composting. If feasible, LCA scopes could even be extended to address currently overlooked issues such as microplastic release during organic waste treatment and the environmental fate of biodegradable fragments [51]. In addition, LCA models could take policy variables (carbon taxes, recycled content mandates) into consideration to identify which levers most effectively influence environmental potential.

Conclusions

In summary, FW-derived bioplastics represent a promising strategy for valorizing waste and reducing reliance on petro-plastics. Under favorable assumptions, using FW as feedstock can generally bring environmental benefits to the bioplastics derived. However, the environmental potential is highly sensitive to life-cycle boundaries, energy sources, and carbon accounting conventions. In many cases, the baseline for comparison and the assumed fate of biogenic carbon determine whether a net benefit is seen. FW-derived bioplastics may not be environmentally benign by default, and the associated potential can be distinguished only with optimized processes and comprehensive LCAs with transparent assumptions. To truly realize potential impact, future research should

prioritize cradle-to-grave, scenario-based LCAs that integrate prospective scale-up, utility recovery systems, regional waste systems, and improved reporting harmonization to credibly guide technological development and policy toward genuinely lower impact, circular bioplastic systems.

CRedit author statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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- * of special interest
- ** of outstanding interest

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